

SANSAN ACTIVITIES MAY TO JULY 2022

WORLD SPIDER CATALOG (WSC)

In the beginning of 2022, a total of 225 species were not yet listed on the WSC for South Africa. During the last three months, 14 Photo Identification Guides (see p. 5) were listed on the WSC, resulting in 53 species now newly recognised to occur in South Africa. The biggest change was for the Araneidae, with 29 species added.

NEW SPECIES

During SANSAN surveys, new species are frequently collected, but to get the new species described and published takes expertise, time and effort. Presently, 2 268 species are listed from 72 families on the South African National Spider Species list. During the report period, the genus *Namundra* Platnick & Bird, 2007 (Prodidomidae), previously known only from Namibia, was added to the South African spider list, as well as new Trochanteriidae and Trachelidae species (see p. 2).

SURVEYS

During the report period, several researchers were involved in surveys or preparing publications with survey results. Some of these surveys are:

- Arachnids of Hogsback in the Eastern Cape (C. Haddad)
- Succulent Karoo in the Northern Cape (C. Haddad)
- Western Soutpansberg (S. Foord)
- Biodiversity of the Waterberg Mountain Complex (T. Bird)
- Kgaswane Nature Reserve (A. Dippenaar-Schoeman for SANSAN News 43);
- Review article on "Spiders in and around houses in South Africa" (A. Dippenaar-Schoeman)
- Spiders of the Gondwana Private Game Reserve (Jolandie Botha and A. Dippenaar-Schoeman)
- Fernkloof Nature Reserve (V. Hamilton Attwell).
- Spider of the Fynbos Biome (A. Dippenaar-Schoeman, unpublished list)
- Spiders of Jeffreys Bay (Linda Wiese and A. Dippenaar-Schoeman)

BEHAVIOUR

Not only is the presence and distribution of species important but also information on their behaviour. With the excellent photographs in circulation we are able to document more on their behaviour. In this issue we report on chelicerae flashing in the Lycosidae (pp. 11–14); web building of *Neoscona moreli* (pp. 23–26) and burrow dwelling in *Asemesthes subnubilus* (pp. 20–22).

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NEW PUBLICATIONS

TWO NEW SPECIES FROM THE NORTHERN CAPE

HADDAD C.R. 2022. Two new dionychan spiders from arid western South Africa (Araneae: Prodidomidae, Trochanteriidae). *Arachnology* 19 (Special Issue): 341–347.

ABSTRACT

As part of a biodiversity survey in the arid western interior of South Africa, two new species of dionychan spiders were collected and are described herein. The prodidomid genus *Namundra* Platnick & Bird, 2007, previously known from arid parts of Namibia and Angola, is recorded from South Africa for the first time, and *N. murphyi* sp. n. is described from a single female. Scanning electron micrographs, based on juvenile specimens only, detail some aspects of the fine morphology of this enigmatic genus for the first time. A new species of the trochanteriid genus *Platyoides* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1891, *P. robertsi* sp. n., is described from three females. DNA barcodes (cytochrome oxidase subunit I, COI) are provided for all of the specimens included in this paper.

Namundra murphyi Haddad, 2022

Distribution: Only known from the type locality Northern Cape, Richtersveld National Park, Akkedis Pass.

Platyoides robertsi Haddad, 2022

Distribution: Only known from two isolated localities in the Northern Cape, Richtersveld National Park, Akkedis Pass, and Calvinia, Akkerendam Nature Reserve.

NEW TRACHELIDAE SOUTH AFRICAN SPECIES

HADDAD C.R., JIN C. & PLATNICK N.I. 2022. A revision of the spider genus *Orthobula* Simon, 1897 (Araneae: Trachelidae) in the Afrotropical Region. I. Continental species. *Zootaxa* 5133(3): 355–382.

ABSTRACT

The continental Afrotropical species of the spider genus *Orthobula* Simon, 1897 are revised. Of the 19 presently described species, only six have been recorded from the Afrotropical Region, three of which were described from continental Africa: *O. calceata* Simon, 1897 from Sierra Leone, *O. milloti* Caporiacco, 1949 from Kenya, and *O. radiata* Simon, 1897 from South Africa (Simon 1897a; Caporiacco 1949). The three currently known species were redescribed, including the first descriptions of the males of *O. calceata* and females of *O. radiata*. Three new species are described from both sexes: *O. aethiopica* sp. nov. from Ethiopia, *O. arca* sp. nov. from South Africa, and *O. marusiki* sp. nov. from West Africa and the western Congo Basin. All of the species are obligate ground dwellers, being particularly common in the leaf litter of woody plants, except for *O. arca*, which prefers open grasslands.

Orthobula arca Haddad, Jin & Platnick, 2022

Distribution: Widespread in the Grassland Biome of central South Africa (Free State, Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal).

Orthobula radiata Simon, 1897

Distribution: A common ground-dwelling spider widespread in Southern Africa sampled from pitfalls and litter in various biomes in Southern Africa, including arid Nama Karoo, grasslands, forests, thickets and savannas. Specimens were regularly sampled near ants' nests (e.g. *Monomorium* and *Tetramorium*), particularly under logs and in leaf litter.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

EFFECT OF SHORT-TERM KRAALING ON SPIDERS

SEBATA S., HADDAD C.R., FITZPATRICK M.J. & FOORD S.H. 2022. Weak negative responses of spider diversity to short-term 'kraaling'. *The Rangeland Journal* 44(2): 61–75 <https://doi.org/10.1071/RJ22004>

ABSTRACT

The influence of short-duration, concentrated kraaling (enclosure) has been documented for plants, wildlife, and macro-invertebrates. However, limited information is available on its impact on ground-dwelling spiders. The purpose of this study was to assess the effect of short-duration kraaling, time since cattle removal, and microhabitat variables on spider assemblages in Matabeleland North province, Zimbabwe. We used a matched-pair and space for time design (inside vs outside previously kraaled inclusions) across 11 sites, using four cattle herds (H1, H6, H7 and HNguni). Spiders were sampled in the early and late rainy season with pitfall traps left open for 14-day sampling periods and emptied twice in each period. We captured 634 spiders, comprising 63 species in 44 genera and 18 families. The most abundant family was Lycosidae (37%; 16 spp.), followed by Gnaphosidae (15%; 10 spp.) and Salticidae (14.5%; 7 spp.). Generalised linear mixed models showed that generic richness was greater in sites with more bare ground; however, this effect was reversed in previously kraaled sites and was particularly evident for spider abundance that responded negatively relative to unkraaled sites. Furthermore, with a U-shaped recovery, generic richness increased with time since kraaling. Model-based multivariate models showed that short-duration kraaling had a significant impact on spider assemblage structure, but this impact was relatively small compared with the effect of seasonality.

Most of the species that made significant contributions to this multivariate response were less diverse in kraaled sites. Spider diversity, therefore, had a weak negative response to short-term kraaling. However, these impacts should also be assessed at broader scales, including areas where cattle go to graze.

Pardosa crassipalpis Photo: Peter Webb

Two species, *P. manubriata* (15%) and *P. crassipalpis* (5%), were the second and third most abundant species sampled, after *Alloccosa umtalica* (32%).

MORE ON A POORLY KNOWN CRAB SPIDER *TMARUS LONGICAUDATUS*

CALATAYUD-MASCARELL A., ALONSO-ALONSO P., BORATYŃSKI Z., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., PABIJAN M. & SALGADO-IRAZABAL X. 2022. Hidden among the prickles: New records and updated distribution of *Tmarus longicaudatus* Millot, 1942 (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Arachnology* 9(1): 1–6.

ABSTRACT

We report the first records of the poorly known crab spider *Tmarus longicaudatus* Millot, 1942 in Mauritania, Namibia and the United Arab Emirates (UAE). The new record in Mauritania extends the distribution of the species by almost 2 750 km to the west from the closest and type locality in Niger. The new record in Namibia is 1 000 km north of the closest locality in South Africa. New records in the UAE are more than 900 km east of the closest locality in central Saudi Arabia. Using all available records, we present the known distribution of the species and its climate-based predicted range, indicating a wide distribution in arid to semi-arid regions. Considering its wide expected distribution, extending throughout Africa and the Arabian Peninsula, integrative taxonomic studies are needed to clarify the species status of this masquerading spider.

Tmarus longicaudatus

Note: Distribution of *T. longicaudatus* in South Africa: **KwaZulu-Natal** : Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61). **Limpopo**: Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam). (-23.37, 29.32). **Western Cape**: Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg (-32.28, 18.53).

FIELD OBSERVATIONS

EFFECT OF FROST ON *ARGIOPE* SPIDERS IN THE FREE STATE

Argiope australis female in web early in the morning in the Free State with temperatures of -3 °C Photo credit: Allen Jones

Allen Jones from Mpetsane Conservancy Estate in the Free State shared with us some interesting information and photographs of the effect of cold on *Argiope* specimens. He wrote:

“We have been having some heavy frost days here with the temperature down to -3 °C when I took these pictures. Several *Argiope australis* females had remained “exposed” in their webs and were covered in frost and frozen dew drops in the early morning. When I stroked them they were VERY cold and did not move at all. I really thought that they were dead. However, a few hours later, after sunshine had “defrosted” them, they were alive and feeding normally. When I stroked them again they ran across their webs away from me. This also happened a few days later and 10 spiders reacted the same. Clearly a case for cryogenic *Argiopes*. We are now down to -7 °C and there are no spiders to be found anywhere except for a few golden orb-web spiders that will be all gone soon.”

Web covered with frost. Photo credit: Allen Jones

Beautiful web of *Leucauge festiva* at Mpetsane Conservancy Estate. Photo credit: Allen Jones

Photo showing the rich diversity of orb-web spiders at Mpetsane Conservancy Estate.: Photo credit: Allen Jones

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

CALATAYUD-MASCARELL A., ALONSO-ALONSO P., BORATYŃSKI Z., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., PABIJAN M. & SALGADO-IRAZABAL X. 2022. Hidden among the prickles: New records and updated distribution of *Tmarus longicaudatus* Millot, 1942 (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Arachnology* 9(1): 1–6.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022a. The Agelenidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 23 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5981186.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022b. The Anyphaenidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 6 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5982411.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022c. The Atypidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 7 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6032638.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022d. The Barychelidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 9 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6033496.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022e. The Ctenidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 17 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6090166.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022f. The Eresidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 46 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6331366.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022g. The Philodromidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 53 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6634009>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022h. The Sparassidae of South Africa. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 71 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6614498.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & JOCQUÉ R. 2022. The Amaurobiidae of South Africa 2022. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 26 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5981342.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & WEBB P. 2022a. The Araneidae of South Africa. Version 2: Part 1 (A-C). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 74 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6326922.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & WEBB P. 2022b. The Araneidae of South Africa. Version 2: Part 2 (E-Ne). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 64 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6619195.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & WEBB P. 2022f. The Araneidae of South Africa. Version 2: Part 3 (Ne-U). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 66 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6326991.

HADDAD C.R. 2022. Two new dionychan spiders from arid western South Africa (Araneae: Prodidomidae, Trochanteriidae). *Arachnology* 19 (Special Issue): 341–347.

HADDAD C.R., JIN C. & PLATNICK N.I. 2022. A revision of the spider genus *Orthobula* Simon, 1897 (Araneae: Trachelidae) in the Afrotropical Region. I. Continental species. *Zootaxa* 5133(3): 355–382.

MARUSIK Y.M. & SHERWOOD D. 2022. Matronymic genera in spiders (Araneae) named for arachnologists. *Arachnology* 19 (Special Issue): 150–157.

SEBATA S., HADDAD C.R., FITZPATRICK M.J. & FOORD S.H. 2022. Weak negative responses of spider diversity to short-term 'kraaling'. *The Rangeland Journal* 44(2): 61–75 doi:10.107/RJ22004.

THE WATERBERG BIOSPHERE: SPIDER CHECKLIST

Over the years, SANSa has been involved in several spiders surveys throughout the Waterberg Biosphere (WB). All these spiders are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) as voucher specimens and >4 000 records are available. From the SANSa and NCA databases the first checklist of spiders of the WB was compiled, listing a total of 558 species.

We were invited by the Waterberg BioQuest / Waterberg Soektog to help to document the diversity of the WB. They have a website <http://www.waterberg-bioquest.co.za> where the information is displayed. A checklist of 502 spider species can be downloaded as well as a large number of images of spiders photographed in the WB.

Notes on two hairy crab spiders *Thomisus granulatus* Karsch, 1880 and *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The two crab spiders *Thomisus granulatus* Karsch, 1880 and *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901 resemble each other and are frequently misidentified. The differences between the two species are discussed and the general morphology of the species is discussed and live photographs are provided, with notes on their lifestyle, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: Afrotropical Region, egg laying, maternal care, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Thomisidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Presently, 38 genera of the Thomisidae represented by 143 species are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Although large numbers of specimens were collected, little is still known about specific generic and species behaviour.

The genus *Thomisus* Walckenaer, 1805 is represented by 143 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2022) and 15 species are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). The genus includes a group of spiders characterised by short, robust bodies, with the first two pairs of legs stout and the lateral eyes situated on distinct eye tubercles. Two of the species are recognised by their hirsute appearance have been identified from the survey samples as *T. granulatus* Karsch, 1880 and *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901.

The two species resemble each other and are frequently misidentified. In this paper we provide more information on the general morphology of both species and live photographs are provided with notes on their lifestyle, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. SANSa made requests for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and several sets of photographs of these two species were received from the public.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Both species are African endemics, with *T. granulatus* described by Karsch (1880) from Malawi and *T. spiculosus* by Pocock, 1901 from Zimbabwe. Both sexes of the two species are known and were revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

The integuments of the females differ in colour as well as the number of tubercles and setae on the body and legs. In *T. granulatus* the body is pale cream and covered by small white tubercles giving it a granulous appearance and some of the tubercles bear short to longer erect spiniform setae (Fig. 3). In *T. spiculosus* there are fewer tubercles but each bears longer and more hair-like setae (Fig. 4) giving it a hirsute appearance and the colour varies from yellow to greenish-grey.

In the males, both species are hirsute but in *T. granulatus* the male is reddish brown (Fig. 5), while in *T. spiculosus* the male resembles the female (Fig. 14).

Figure 1–4. Female: 1. *Thomisus granulatus* dorsal view. 2. *T. spiculosus* dorsal view. 3. *T. granulatus* eye pattern. 4. *T. spiculosus* eye pattern. Photo credits: 1. Bruce Blake. 2. Peter Webb. 3. Desiré Pelser. 4. Peter Webb.

***Thomisus granulatus* Karsch, 1880**

Thomisus granulatus Karsch, 1880: 382; Lessert, 1923: 173; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 15; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022: 50. *Thomisus hystrix* Lawrence, 1947: 25 (name preoccupied, Nicolet, 1849).

Thomisus lawrencei Roewer, 1951: 449 (replacement name); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 15 (synonym).

Diagnostic characteristics: Female (Figs 5, 7, 10). Size: Total length 9–10 mm. Integument: body and legs covered with numerous small polyp-like tubercles, of which the tips are white; each tubercle provided with a spiniform seta (Fig. 7). Colour of body and legs creamish white, the small tubercles giving it a spotted appearance. Carapace translucent with a white broad medial band; eye area with brown triangle area (Fig. 3). Abdomen creamy white with strong abdominal tubercles (Figs 5 & 7). Epigyne circular, varies slightly in shape between individuals (Fig. 10).

Male much smaller than female (Figs 5–6). Size: TL 3 mm. Colour of carapace, abdomen reddish brown; clothed with strong setae (Fig. 6); area around eyes paler. Abdomen also with tubercles. Legs: coxae, trochanters and femora of legs I and II same colour as carapace; patellae, tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II blackish brown; tibiae with dense setae; rest of legs like carapace. Palp with retrolateral apophysis triangular in shape (Figs 8–9).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Botswana, Malawi, Namibia, Zambia, Swaziland, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Fort Grey (-33.19, 27.12); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.27, 30.02); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Gate (-28.1, 32.45); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Kosi Bay (-28.33, 31.08); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Lake Sibhayi (-27.35, 32.7); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Nyala Game Reserve (-28.72, 31.88); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Shakaskraal (-29.41, 31.26); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umzumbe (-30.61, 30.54); Makatini Flats (-27.25, 32.22); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Nyala Game Reserve (-28.33, 31.08); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Umzumbe (-30.61, 30.54); Gilboa Plantation, Natal Midlands (-29.25, 30.34); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Gravelotte (-23.95, 30.57); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Luvuvhu Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Malipsdrift (-24.22, 29.83); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Strydom Tunnel (-24.4, 30.61); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Tshulu (Venda) 2.58, 30.81); Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95).

Mpumalanga: Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Hector-spruit (-25.43, 31.68); Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Witrivier (-25.31, 31.02).

Western Cape: Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

Figures 5–7. *Thomisus granulatus*: 5. Female with red male on her abdomen. 6. Male anterior view. 7. Female from Lephahlale dorsal view. Photo credits: 5–6. Bruce Blake. 7. Peter Webb.

Figures 8–10. *Thomisus granulatus*: 8–9. Male palp ventral view. 10. Epigyne. Credits: 9. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 8 & 10. Line drawings after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

***Thomisus spiculosus* Pocock, 1901**

Thomisus spiculosus Pocock, 1901: 340; Comellini, 1957: 27; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 11; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022: 59.

Thomisus dottrensi Comellini, 1957: 10, f. 18–19 (synonym)

Diagnostic characteristics: Female (Figs 11–15). Total length 7–8 mm. Integument: body and legs covered with numerous long, spiniform setae, each seta situated on a small tubercle; some setae, as well as their bases, darker than rest. Carapace fawn with pale green to grey broad bands over carapace; eye region with reddish triangle; carapace high, slightly wider than long; both eye rows recurved, anterior row more so than posterior row. Abdomen fawn with a yellowish tint; also with strong abdominal tubercles; decorated dorsally with five pale spots. Epigynum oval with medium septum (Fig. 15). Male. TL 3–6 mm. Colour of carapace dark brown, slightly darker around edge (Fig. 12); chelicerae dark brown; abdomen yellowish brown; legs same colour as carapace except metatarsi and tarsi I and II, which are slightly paler in colour than rest of legs. Palp tibiae with short median and retro-lateral apophyses (Fig. 14).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Democratic Republic of the Congo, Nigeria, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36).

KwaZulu-Natal: Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Blydepoort (-24.74, 30.58); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Leydsdorp, Shilowani (-23.98, 30.53); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Shewasaula, Mt Sibasa (-23.5, 30.37); Luvhondo Nature reserve (-23.04, 29.44); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Mphaphuli Cycad Reserve (-22.42, 30.49); Lephallale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93).

Mpumalanga: Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82).

CONSERVATION MEASURES

***Thomisus granulatus*:** There are no known threats to the species and in South Africa it is recorded from several protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2008) and Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001). No conservation actions are recommended.

***Thomisus spiculosus*:** There are no known threats to the species and it is protected in the following reserves: Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Makalali Game Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001), Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.* 2016) and Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

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Figures 11–15. *Thomisus spiculosus*: 11. Female dorsal view. 12. Male dorsal view. 13. Female anterior view. 14. Male palp. 15. Epigyne. Photo credits: 11–13. Bruce Blake. 14–15. Line drawings of genitalia after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983)

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Figures 16–18. *Thomisus granulatus*: 16. Female on egg sac. 17–18. Female with spiderlings. Photo credits: 16–17. John Richter. 18. Desiré Pelser.

BEHAVIOUR

The two species occur sympatrically several localities. They are free-living plant dwellers sampled during beating and sweeping from vegetation. They have been sampled from all the floral biomes except the more arid biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). It was also sampled in citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Several images of the females of *T. granulatus* were received showing the female on her egg sac that she attached to the underside of a leaf (Fig. 20). The female takes up position on the egg sac where she stays until the spiderlings emerge. Several photographs were taken showing the spiderlings crawling over her body but their presence does not seem to bother her (Figs 21–22). Adults were sampled from September to December, and males during November and December. As predators they feed on a variety of insects, such as Lantana bugs (Fig. 19).

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Figures 19. *Thomisus spiculosis* female feeding on Lantana bugs. Photo credit: Desiré Pelser.

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Interesting behaviour of two wolf spiders *Hogna spenceri* and *H. transvaalica* in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: Chelicerae flashing, an interesting behaviour observed in the wolf spiders *Hogna spenceri* (Pocock, 1898) and *H. transvaalica* (Simon, 1898), is discussed. Both species are African endemics. The general morphology of the species is discussed and photographs of live specimens are provided showing how the chelicerae colour changes. Notes on their lifestyle, distribution and conservation status are provided.

Key words: Afrotropical Region, burrow dwellers, chelicerae flashing, defense mechanism, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Lycosidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Presently, 24 Lycosidae genera represented by 110 species are known from South Africa. Since the use of pitfall trap in terrestrial invertebrate surveys, the number of lycosids in spider collections has increased dramatically. Although large numbers of specimens have been collected, little is still known about specific generic and species behaviour.

Some of the larger lycosids belong to the genus *Hogna* Simon, 1885. This large genus is represented by 234 species (World Spider Catalog, 2022) and presently 13 species are recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). In this paper we provide more information on the general morphology of *Hogna spenceri* (Pocock, 1898) and *H. transvaalica* (Simon, 1898) with notes on their lifestyle, some interesting defense mechanisms, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. As part of SANSa, requests were made for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and several sets of photographs of *Hogna* spp. have been received from the public.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Members of *Hogna* belong to the subfamily Lycosinae. This subfamily is still poorly known and one of the most diverse in the Afrotropical region. The 13 species recorded from South Africa have not yet been revised. *H. spenceri* and *H. transvaalica* are two species that have been sampled with pitfall traps during several SANSa surveys in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011, Haddad *et al.*, 2013). Series of photographs were received from seven localities.

Both species are large spiders (22 mm) and have the typical *Hogna* eye pattern, with the width of the bottom row of eyes less than the width of the two largest eyes in the middle row (Fig. 3). They occur sympatric and are recorded from seven of the nine South African provinces. The two species resemble each other, with only the dorsal abdominal pattern (Figs 1, 2) and ventrum (Figs 5 & 14) that differ as well as the genitalia. In both species the setae on the chelicerae change colour when the carapace is tilted backwards. The chelicerae are normally the same colour as the carapace (Fig. 1), but when the carapace is tilted backwards, the setae on the chelicerae change colour (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. *Hogna spenceri* female dorsal view Photo: Peter Webb

Figure 2. *Hogna transvaalica* female dorsal view. Photo: Peter Webb

Figure 3. *Hogna transvaalica* female showing the eye pattern Photo: Peter Webb

Figures 4–5. *Hogna spenceri* female: 3. Dorsal view. 4. Ventral view. Photo credits: Peter Webb

Hogna spenceri (Pocock, 1898)

Lycosa spenceri Pocock, 1898: 313; Lessert, 1915: 60.

Hogna spenceri Roewer, 1955: 251; Roewer, 1959: 463; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 67.

Diagnostic characteristics: Cephalothorax fawn with two lateral dark bands and narrow marginal dark band. Eye field fawn. Abdomen dorsally fawn with blackish inverted V-shaped dark marking anteriorly; mark bordered by broad fawn bands (Figs 4 & 6); markings extend posteriorly in series of dark chevrons. Ventral abdomen, as well as sternum and coxae, deep black, remaining leg links pale yellow, unspotted; chelicerae dark brown, lightly hairy frontal. Total length 22 mm (Roewer 1960).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Hogna spenceri is an African endemic described by Pocock (1898) as *Lycosa spenceri* from Durban. The species is also known from Rwanda and Swaziland.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74; 28.19); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.87, 28.22); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29.00, 29.87); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); iSimangaliso Wetland park uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.62, 32.25). **Limpopo:** Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Molle Molle (-24.65, 28.67); Vhembe Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.13, 29.93); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (-23.12, 29.55); Vhembe Biosphere Mashovelo Lodge (-22.94, 29.88); Western Soutpansberg (-22.95, 29.87); Ellisras/Lephalale (-27.71, 23.32). **Mpumalanga:** Carolina Farm Nooitgedacht (-26.06, 30.11). **North West:** Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97). **North-eastern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162).

Hogna transvaalica known distribution

Figure 6–10. *Hogna spenceri*: 6. Female line drawing after Roewer, (1959). 7. Palp. 8–9. Palp and epigyne line drawing after Roewer (1959). 10. Epigyne.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in six protected areas: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide geographical range, it is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

Hogna transvaalica (Simon, 1898)

Lycosa transvaalica Simon, 1898. *Hogna transvaalica* Roewer, 1955: 252; Roewer, 1959: 468; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 68.

Diagnostic characteristics: Cephalothorax fawn to grey with two dark brown lateral bands and narrow marginal dark lateral bands with three pale striae on both sides. Eye field fawn. Abdomen dorsally fawn with broad median band consisting of marking anteriorly; mark bordered by broad fawn bands (Figs 11 & 12); markings extend posteriorly in series of dark chevrons. Ventral abdomen, as well as sternum and coxae, deep black, but decorated by six white spots (Fig. 13 & 14); two on epigastric areas and four on remaining area. Legs pale yellow to grey, unspotted. Total length 20 mm

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

A Southern African endemic described by Simon (1898) as *Lycosa transvaalica* with type locality given only as “Africa australis Bechuanaland, Griqualand W., Transvaal”. Presently reported from South Africa and Botswana.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in 11 protected areas: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler, 2018); Tsalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003; Robertson *et al.* 2011). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide geographical range, it is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

Figures 11–15. *Hogna transvaalica* female: 11. Female (Photo: Peter Webb). 12.–13. Female habitus dorsal and ventral view after Roewer (1959). 14. Abdomen ventral view (Photo: Peter Webb). 15. Epigyne after Roewer (1959).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.171, 26.5). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Wolfkop (-29.08, 26.04); Naval Hill, Hangmanskloof (-29.06, 26.14); Oliewenhuis Art Museum, Grant's Hill (-29.06, 26.13); Schoemansdrif (-26.58, 27.13); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Tussen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.29, 26.07). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74; 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.87, 28.22); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **Limpopo:** Makapansgat (-24.15, 29.18); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lephahlale Nature Reserve (-23.67, 27.71).

Mpumalanga: Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park: Skukuza (-25.00, 31.97); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.56, 24.16); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3, 22.44); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82).

BEHAVIOUR

Hogna species are known to live in open burrows. While photographing them it was observed that in some species the colour of the setae on the chelicerae change in colour from fawn (Fig. 16) to a signal red (Fig 21) when the carapace is tilted. The chelicerae are normally the same colour as the carapace, but when in danger they tilt the carapace backwards and the setae on the chelicerae become a flaming orange-red colour (Figs 16–22). This probably acts as a warning to enemies.

The colour change of the chelicerae was also seen in the males. In Figs 23–24 the red setae on the old exuviae of a male *H. transvaalica* can be seen.

Some of the other *Hogna* species photographed that do not show any cheliceral colour change include *H. adjacens* Roewer, 1959; *H. lawrencei* (Roewer, 1960); *H. simoni* Roewer, 1959 and *H. zuluana* Roewer, 1959.

Figures 16–21. *Hogna* spp. showing how the chelicerae change in colour. 16–19. *H. spenceri*. 20–22. *H. transvaalica*. Photo credit: Peter Webb

Figures 23–24. *Hogna transvaalica* male exuviae showing the coloured setae on the chelicerae.

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First record of the crab spider *Diaea rohani* Fage, 1923 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT

The crab spider *Diaea rohani* Fage, 1923 was previously known only from Angola. It has now been recorded from South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from Angola to South Africa. This species is possibly undercollected and is suspected to occur in more countries. The general morphology of the species is discussed and photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Diaea* Thorell (1869) is represented by 46 species and nine are known from Africa (World Spider Catalogue, 2022). During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), surveys were undertaken throughout the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and large numbers of thomisids have been sampled. The species *Diaea rohani* Fage, 1923 previously known only from Angola has been recorded for the first time from South Africa.

The general morphology of the male is discussed based on live specimens. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division. SANSa made requests for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and several photographs of the species were received from the public.

TAXONOMY

Diaea rohani Fage, 1923

Diaea rohani Fage, 1923: 224; Fage, 1925: 194; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022: 24.

Diagnostic characteristics: *Diaea rohani* is a small to medium-sized spider, known only from the male (Figs 1–3 & 9). Male: total length 4–5 mm. Carapace varies from fawn to pale green, with two narrow brown lateral bands stretching from the posterior lateral eyes to near to the posterior edge; eye area white; carapace with scattered long setae. Abdomen white, decorated with a broad median pale brown band almost covering dorsal area with two white lateral irregular bands covering about two-thirds the length and four to five black spots (Figs 7–8); dorsum with numerous strong setae. Legs fawn, similar to carapace; only two anterior legs with half of tibiae, metatarsi and tarsi dark; legs with numerous scattered setae especially on femora. Palp with long retrolateral apophysis with tip curved (Figs 4–6).

Juvenile: In an immature female (Fig. 10) the carapace was a pale green without bands; abdomen same as male; legs pale green.

Figures 1–3. *Diaea rohani*: 1 & 2. Male from Wakefield farm. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–8. *Diaea rohani*: 4–6. Male palp. 7–8. Male habitus. Photo credits: 4 & 7. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 5, 6, 8. After Fage (1925).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Angola and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Maclear (-31.08, 28.35). **Free State:** Zastron farm Opnek (-30.29, 27.09). **Gauteng:** KwaMhlanga (-25.42, 28.70). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Wakefield farm near Howick (-29.26, 29.56); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088).

Figures 9–10. *Diaea rohani*: 9. Male from Kloof. 10. Immature female from Aardvark Nature Reserve. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant-dwelling spiders that are more commonly found on shrubs and herbs. They were sampled with sweeping and beating of the vegetation from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Grassland Biomes.

CONSERVATION

From South Africa the species is recorded from five provinces and it is protected in Aardvark Nature Reserve. Although the female still need to be described, the species has a wide range and no threats are known it is listed as Least Concern.

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New records of the crab spider *Hewittia gracilis* Lessert, 1928 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The genus *Hewittia* Lessert, 1928 is newly recorded in South Africa, extending its current distribution range from Central Africa to South Africa. Prior to this study, only the female of the type species *Hewittia gracilis* was known. Photographs of the spider in life and some notes of its behaviour, distribution and conservation status are provided.

Key words: biodiversity; distribution; South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

Hewittia Lessert, 1928 is a small monotypic genus, endemic to Africa, and known only from a female described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large areas in South Africa were surveyed and a series of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Although *Hewittia gracilis* was already listed in the South African Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1018), it was not yet formally reported from South Africa in the World Spider Catalog.

In this paper we report on *H. gracilis* from South Africa. Photographs of live specimens are provided as well as notes on its behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHOD

The specimens examined are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. As part of SANSA, requests were made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and several images were received and are displayed here.

TAXONOMY

Hewittia gracilis Lessert, 1928

Hewittia gracilis Lessert, 1928: 307; Jézéquel, 1964: 111; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010; 2014: 238.

Diagnostic characteristics: Total length: 3–4 mm. Female (Figs 1–2) carapace longer than wide, with scattered short setae and few longer setae present on truncated posterior edge of carapace, on the clypeal edge and between the lateral eyes, and behind posterior lateral eyes; cephalic region high, slightly convex, sloping anteriorly; thoracic region truncated posteriorly. Eyes (Figs 4–5) in two rows covering most of carapace width; both eye rows recurved; anterior eye row slightly wider than posterior eye row; lateral eyes on separate closely situated tubercles; anterior median eyes smallest, a third smaller than anterior lateral eyes; anterior median eyes closer to anterior lateral eyes than to each other, separated by four times their diameter; posterior median eyes a third smaller than posterior lateral eyes, separated by six times their diameter from each other; median ocular quadrangle slightly wider than long, narrower anteriorly than posteriorly.

Figures 1–3. *Hewittia gracilis*: 1. Female lateral view. 2. Female dorsolateral view. 3. Undescribed male lateral view. Photo credits: Rudi Steenkamp.

Figures 4–11. *Hewittia gracilis* female: 4. Alcohol material dorsal view. 5. Dorsal view carapace. 6. Epigyne ventral view. 7. Epigyne dorsal view. 8. Epigyne line drawing. 9. Carapace lateral view. 10. Carapace dorsal view. 11. Carapace anterior view. Photo credits: 4–7 Robin Lyle. 8–11 After Lessert (1928).

Abdomen oval, bluntly truncated anteriorly, a third longer than wide; colour of abdomen varies from grayish white with two posterior dark spots to almost total brown but always with the thin white line circling the dorsal area. Leg formula 1243. Epigyne with a circular opening (Figs 6–8). On photo of the undescribed male the carapace is reddish brown and abdomen grey with a pink tint and distinct white bands (Fig. 3)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Democratic Republic of the Congo (Lessert), Ivory Coast (Jezequel, 1964). New: Namibia (NCA), South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Free State National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Rietvlei (-29.18, 30.33); Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.359, 30.64). **Limpopo:** Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73). **Mpumalanga:** Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97). **Northern Cape:** Kuruman (-27.50, 23.30). **North West:** Kgawane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.75); Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08). **Western Cape:** Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 28.48); Kirstenbosch National Garden (-23.67, 28.38); 40 km NE of Ceres, Touwsriver road (-33.36, 19.31).

Hewittia gracilis known distribution in South Africa

CONSERVATION

The species is protected in eight reserves such as Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989) and Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008) as well as two national parks (Kruger National Park and Table Mountain National Park). No conservation actions are recommended. More sampling needed to collect male.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant dwellers. They are mainly active during the day and their robust front legs enable them to attack prey much larger than themselves. Although widely distributed, they are not very commonly found. They were collected by beating shrubs and sweep netting grasses in South Africa from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

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Observations on the Kalahari ground spider *Asemesthes subnubilus* Simon, 1887 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae)

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ABSTRACT: The flat-bellied ground spiders of the genus *Asemesthes* Simon, 1887 are represented by 26 species, of which 25 are known from Southern Africa and 18 from South Africa. Although commonly sampled, little is still known about their behaviour. *Asemesthes subnubilus* Simon, 1887, commonly known as the Kalahari ground spider, was sampled from several localities in the Northern and Western Cape provinces of South Africa. The general morphology of both sexes is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), Succulent Karoo Biome

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Asemesthes* Simon, 1887, represented by 26 species, is known from Angola, Namibia and South Africa, with only a single species described from Ethiopia (World Spider Catalog, 2022). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), spiders were sampled throughout the country over a period of 23 years (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). A large number of *Asemesthes* specimens were sampled during pitfall surveys, and among them *A. subnubilus* Simon, 1887 has been identified. The general morphology of both sexes is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

As part of SANSa, requests were made for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and several sets of photographs of *A. subnubilus* were received from the public. Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Asemesthes subnubilus Simon, 1887

Asemesthes subnubilus Simon, 1887: 373 (juv); Simon, 1893: 384, 340; Dalmas, 1921: 317, (juv); Tucker, 1923: 301; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010: 287.

Asemesthes aureus Purcell, 1908: 242; Dalmas, 1921: 317 (synonym); Tucker, 1923: 288.

Asemesthes subnubilus, the type species of *Asemesthes*, is a Southern African endemic described by Simon (1887) from the Kalahari, but unfortunately based on juvenile specimens. A second species, *A. aureus*, described by Purcell (1908) from the Kalahari too, was synonymised with *A. subnubilus* by Dalmas (1921). The only drawing available of the species is the eye pattern by Dalmas (1921). However, the presence of golden setae across the body without pronounced darker markings, noted in several descriptions, is found in only a single *Asemesthes* species on the subcontinent.

Diagnostic characteristics: Female: total length 5–6mm. Carapace integument dark brown, clothed with fawn to yellow appressed setae (Figs 1-4), in some with intermingled white setae (Fig. 9); fovea not distinct (Fig. 3); clypeus with strong, forward-directed setae (Fig. 3). Eyes in two rows; anterior row only slightly procurved, slightly wider than posterior row; posterior row strongly recurved; lateral eyes larger than median eyes in both rows; median eyes smaller than lateral eyes; anterior lateral eyes largest, followed by posterior lateral eyes, with posterior median eyes smallest; median ocular quadrangle longer than wide, narrower posteriorly (Figs 1, 3).

Figures 1–4. *Asemesthes subnubilus*: 1,3 Female and 2. Male from Aardvark Nature Reserve. 4. Male from Richtersveld. Photo credits: 1–3. Peter Webb. 4. Charles Haddad.

Figures 5–8. *Asemesthes subnubilus*: 5. Female habitus, dorsal view. 6. Male habitus, dorsal view. 7. Male palp, ventral view. 8. Female epigyne, ventral view. Photos: Charles Haddad.

Abdomen integument brown, clothed with golden-yellow appressed setae; spinnerets darker (Fig. 9). Legs dark, with similar appressed setae as carapace, but less dense; all legs with numerous erect scattered setae, but tarsi paler. Epigyne (Fig. 8): with tongue-like median scape and atrium broader than long. Male: total length: 4-5 mm. Similar to female, but slightly darker, more slender and smaller in size (Fig. 6). Palp (Fig. 7): tegulum ovoid, embolus originating proximally, curving around prolateral margin, associated with membranous conductor distally.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa, Namibia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

SOUTH AFRICA. Northern Cape: Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.40); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73.); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Namaqua National Park (-30.017, 17.579); Akkerendam Nature Reserve (-31.433, 19.783); Upington (-28.435, 21.305); Jakkalsputs (-28.67, 16.95); Tankwa-Karoo National Park (-32.28, 19.82). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088).

BEHAVIOUR

Asemesthes subnubilus are free-running ground dwellers and they were sampled from the Succulent Karoo Biome. In Upington the species was observed in a sandy patch. They were found in small burrows made in the sand. A silk funnel covers the entrance with plant matter sometimes sticking to the silk (Fig. 11). The spiders can be seen in the burrow (Fig. 12) but they are shy and are not easy to catch. At the Aardvark Nature Reserve the entrance to a burrow was photograph showing the shape and area it covers (Fig. 10).

Figures 9–13. *Asemesthes subnubilus*: 9. Female, dorsal view of body. 10. Burrow with funnel-shaped silk entrance. 11. Female in burrow. 12. Female in burrow entrance. 13. Female, dorsal view. Photo credits: 9–10. Peter Webb; 11–12. Cecile Roux. 13. Judd Kirkel.

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Notes on the grass orb-web spider *Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract: *Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863) is an African endemic species that was introduced to Cuba and Argentina. Information on their behaviour, general morphology and distribution in South Africa with photographs on their webs and lifestyle are provided.

Key words: Free State; South African National Survey of Arachnida; web building

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Neoscona* is represented by 116 species (World Spider Catalog, 2022) and 17 species are recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Large numbers of *Neoscona* specimens were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). One of these species, *Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863), is commonly found making orb-webs in grass and can be recognised by the abdominal pattern and slightly elongated abdomen (Fig.1). The species was originally described as *Epeira morelii* from Reunion. It is a species with a wide distribution known from the Afrotropical Region as well as from Cuba to Argentina (Grasshoff, 1980).

Neoscona moreli are very colourful spiders and were sampled from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022). In this paper, we provide information on the distribution of *N. moreli* with observations and photographs taken in the field over a period of several years.

METHOD

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys over a period of 20 years are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Observation on their behaviour was carried out in grassland at the Mpetsane Conservancy Estate (MCE), which is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands some 14 km from Clocolan. The MCE (28°48'S; 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop) sanctuary and nature reserve. The first author (AJ), while staying on the estate, is able to regularly walk in the estate to photograph spiders and make observations (Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2021).

TAXONOMY

Neoscona moreli (Vinson, 1863)

Epeira morelii Vinson, 1863: 166, 309

Neoscona moreli Grasshoff, 1980: 407 (removed mf from Synonymy of *N. theisi*); 1986: 56; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg 2010: 25; 2014: 62.

For more, see World Spider Catalog: <https://wsc.nmbe.ch/species/4898>

Diagnostic characteristics: Size TL: male 6–8 mm; female 8–16 mm. Female: carapace elongate, slightly longer than wide, narrower in eye region; fawn with brown median band and two lateral bands (Fig. 1); covered with white setae; eyes eight in two rows (4:4). Abdomen elongate-oval, overhanging the carapace; with distinct longitudinal bands; broad median white band bordered by scalloped darker bands, followed by white band (Figs 1, 3 & 9); sides mottled. Ventrally abdomen with dark median band bordered by six white markings; posterior pair smallest (Figs 4 & 10).

Figures 1–2. *Neoscona moreli* 1. Immature male. 2. Female in orb-web. Photo credits: Allen Jones.

Figures 3–8. *Neoscona moreli* 3. Abdomen dorsal view. 4. Abdomen ventral view. 5. Epigyne drawing. 6. Epigyne. 7. Leg II. 8. Tibiae 1–11.3–5,8 After Grasshoff (1986). 6 & 7 Peter Webb

Legs of medium length, with strong setae; kept close to the body when at rest; fawn with distinct bands and spots (Figs 9–11). In male tibiae I with strong setae; tibiae II with dense short dense setae prolaterally (Figs 7–8). Female epigyne with long scapus (Figs 5–6).

Neoscona moreli can be confused with other grass orb-web spiders such as *Kilima decens* and *Larinia* species that are also straw-coloured with bands on their abdomen.

HABITAT

The species is a very common grassland species that was sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). The species was also sampled from avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), pecans and pistachio orchards (Haddad *et al.*, 2005), and cotton (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999), lucerne, maize and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

BEHAVIOUR

Neoscona moreli are common inhabitants of grasses where they construct orb-webs in low vegetation between the grasses (Figs 13–14). They are found in the field from September to May. Spiderlings hatch in January to February and when still very small, just a few mm in size and they built their own webs. They grow quickly when a regular food supply is available. They catch midges and small flies. By the end of March they are full size already. They usually construct their webs at sunset in the evening, (Fig. 2) and dismantle them the following morning. They are procryptic by day, resting with their bodies appressed to vegetation where they blend in with their elongated, straw-coloured bodies (Figs 1 & 12). They are gregarious and sometimes present in large numbers.

Figures 9–14. *Neoscona moreli*: 9. Female dorsal view. 10. Female ventral view. 11–12. Male. 13. Orb-web in grass. 14. Female in web. Photo credits: Allen Jones.

Some specimens sometimes do remain in the web also during the day and catch flies (Fig. 15). The webs are about 200 mm in diameter and made about 300 mm above ground level. The web consists of a bridge line attached to grasses. The number of radii varies from 21 to 31 and a circular area is made of adhesive threads. They feed on moths (Fig. 17), beetles (Fig. 16), flies (Fig. 18) and grasshoppers (Fig. 19). Males very similar to female and make their own webs (Fig. 11).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Widespread throughout Africa. Introduced to the Caribbean, Colombia, Venezuela to Argentina.

Global distribution after Grasshoff (1980).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: East London (-33.01, 27.9); Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Fort Grey Nature Reserve (-33.19, 27.12); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37). **Free State:** Clarens (Farm Adullam) (-28.51, 28.43); Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.92, 27.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Fouriesburg (Mooifontein) (-28.61, 28.23); Golden Gate Nature Reserve (-28.5, 28.62); Ventersburg (-28.08, 27.14); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **Gauteng:** Bon Accord (-25.62, 28.2); Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Centurion (Irene) (-25.85, 28.16); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Modderfontein (-26.08, 28.17); Moloto (-25.46, 28.63); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Van Riebeeck Nature Reserve (25.85, 28.16); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.85, 28.16); Dinokeng (-25.4, 28.38); Heidelberg (-26.5, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.97, 29.46); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Ngoye Forest (-28.88, 31.38); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Kamborg Nature Reserve, Fernwood Field Centre (-29.39, 29.67). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Meetsa-A-Bophelo Mission Station (-24.25, 30.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93);

Figures 15–19. *Neoscona moreli*: 15. Female in orb-web covered with dew early in the morning. 16. Female feeding on a beetle. 17. Feeding on a moth. 18. Feeding on a fly. 19 Feeding on a grasshopper. Photo credits: Allen Jones.

Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Delmas (Farm Rietvallei) (26.08, 28.57); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.1); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Hendrina (-26.15, 29.71); ; Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Kroondal (-75, 27.32); Kgawane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Noup (-30.13, 17.2). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park(-32.28, 22.46).

CONSERVATION

There are no known threats to the species. In South Africa it was sampled from the following protected areas: Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999); Makelali Nature Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2013) and Mpetsane Conservation Estate (Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2022).

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